

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D1.2 Management and quality plan – Year 2

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Acknowledgements

This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the AfriConEU consortium.

Glossary and Abbreviations	
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DM	Dissemination Manager
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IM	Innovation Manager
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project Coordinator
QM	Quality Manager
SC	Steering Committee
SO	Specific Objectives
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive Summary

The Management and Quality Plan is a document that aims to provide the AfriConEU consortium with a guide of best practices that support partners in the administrative and financial management of the project while ensuring the quality of the project outcomes.

This document comprises the second version of the Management and Quality Plan which includes some parts from the first version (D1.1, submitted in M2) with updates and additions derived from the course of action of the project, as follows:

- Information about the amendment request to the GA on June 2021;
- Status of the Project Management Structure and respective roles and responsibilities;
- Updates on the internal communication channels used and deviations from the planned procedures for physical meetings;
- Update on the internal and external reporting periods outputs;
- Update on the table of deliverables' revision (correction of some typos and updates from the amendment to the GA);
- Update on the status of the risk management template.

The Plan will be updated and changed according to the evolution of procedures and progress one more time, by Month 30.

1. Introduction

1.1 About AfriConEU

The AfriConEU project was created with the intent to reinforce, foster, enable and strengthen the digital innovation ecosystems in Africa through international partnerships and collaborations by targeting DIHs in selected African and European countries to build a meaningful network of people to ensure the growth and a thriving digital innovation ecosystem in both continents.

The main goal of the project is to develop, test, and validate the “AfriConEU Networking Academy”, an innovative mechanism for connecting and sharing best practices, experiences, and resources between DIHs in Africa and between DIHs in Africa and the EU, in a comprehensive, replicable, and self-sustaining way. Through two flagship programmes — “Capacity Building” and “Transcontinental Partnership Development” —, the AfriConEU Networking Academy intends to empower and enable African DIHs to best serve their local industry, boost their start-up ecosystem and empower the youth population with the necessary skills to thrive in a digitalized world.

1.2 Objectives of D1.2

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP1 and intends to be an updated version of the document describing management and quality procedures that were defined at the beginning of the project in D1.1 (M2). To recall, the objective of the Management and Quality Plan is to support partners in the effective and efficient administrative and financial management of the project while ensuring the quality of the project outcomes. It presents the procedures, structures and coordination defined for the project implementation and sets out key responsibilities for partners. It is intended to support the achievement of project objectives, the compliance with the project schedule and the timely delivery of project results.

1.3 Targets of D1.2

This deliverable is addressed mainly to the AfriConEU consortium partners in order to offer a comprehensive and standardised set of best practice procedures that will ensure a smooth and efficient project management and coordination.

1.4 Methodology

The AfriConEU Management and Quality Plan is ruled by the following principles that ensure a Successful Project Management:

- ✓ Good communication between partners is of paramount importance to the success of the project;
- ✓ Ensure that more than one person in each partner organization is aware of what is going on in each of the specific tasks;
- ✓ Elaborate drafts before the deadlines and follow up on all the deliverables;
- ✓ Flexible assignments, parallel tasks, full-time persons can adapt fast to changes in project workload;
- ✓ Promote the project and its interest to the right stakeholders to initiate the collaboration and have more easy access to information.

2. Essential Documents

The fundamental binding rules that apply to the AfriConEU project are set out in the following documents, signed by all consortium partners:

- Grant Agreement (and its Annexes);
- Consortium Agreement.

2.1. Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (GA) was signed between the Project Coordinator (PC) and the European Commission (EC) in January 2021 (before the project started) and by project partners through the Accession Form A.

In June 2021, an amendment was requested to perform some changes on the work plan, including the duration of a specific task and delivery of correspondent deliverable and changes to milestones. The details of this request are presented in the table below:

Table 1 - Changes to the GA requested on 01/06/2021

Page/section	Nature of change and reason (if applicable)
Part 3 / Implementation	
	The Gantt chart has been updated to reflect the changes made to the duration of WP2
	MS5 was rescheduled to Month 20
	MS11 was removed
	WP2 end date was updated to Month 11. Task 2.3 was updated to start on Month 5 and end on Month 11
	D2.4 was updated and will be delivered on Month 11
	WP4 the lead beneficiary has been corrected to INOVA+
	Typos were corrected in the name of deliverables D2.1 and D5.2

It should be noted that the required changes did not impact the overall budget and grant, i.e. the total amount did not change.

Details about the distinct specific parts of the GA are explained in [D1.1](#).

2.2. Consortium Agreement

As stated in D1.1, the Consortium Agreement (CA) establishes the rules that govern the relations between partners (for example: management structures and decision-making processes within the project, distribution of the Community financial contribution, rules on dissemination, use and access rights, settlement of internal disputes, etc.).

To date, the CA has not been amended in any way, as no necessary changes have been identified by any of the project partners, whether related to the structure of the project, rules of exploitation or protection of the knowledge generated, among others.

Partners continue to be reminded and encouraged to read this document carefully whenever necessary and follow the agreed rules.

3. Project Management Structure

The overall management structure of the AfriConEU project is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – AfriConEU Management Structure

All people identified as key personnel to take up the roles and responsibilities of Steering Committee (SC), Project Coordinator (PC), Project Management Office (PMO), Quality Manager (QM), Innovation Manager (IM), Dissemination Manager (DM), Work Packages Leaders (WPL) and Advisory Board (AB) in D1.1 continue to ensure their duties within the AfriConEU ecosystem, as indicated in the table below:

Table 2 - Project Management Structure roles

Role	Partner	Representative of the Partner
Members of the Steering Committee	INOVA+	Miguel Sousa
	ECA	Peace Odili
	YMH	Marilena Maragkou
	PBS	Catarina Reis
	OUTBOX	Richard Zulu
	DPIXEL	Stefano Azzalin
	STIMMULI	Irene Kalemaki
	ITC	Sasa Straus
	BUNI	Edwin Bakalemwa
	ATBN	Eunice Ball

	HAPA	Gideon Brefo*
Project Coordinator	INOVA+	Miguel Sousa
Project Management Office	INOVA+	Ana Solange Leal
Quality Manager	STIMMULI	Ioanna Garefi
Quality Expert	INOVA+	Marta Coto
Innovation Manager	PBS	Rui Coutinho
Dissemination Manager	YMH	Marilena Maragkou
WP1 Leader	INOVA+	Miguel Sousa
WP2 Leader	ATBN	Eunice Ball
WP3 Leader	PBS	Rui Coutinho
WP4 Leader	INOVA+	Ana Solange Leal
WP5 Leader	BUNI	Edwin Bakalemwa
WP6 Leader	YMH	Marilena Maragkou
Members of the Advisory Board	Eurico Neves	
	Gil Gonçalves	
	Angelos Liapis	

* Gideon Brefo has replaced Douglas Boateng as a member of the steering committee.

For an extensive description of each of the specific roles and responsibilities within the AfriConEU management structure as well as the curricula of each of the individuals indicated in the table below, please consult [D1.1](#).

4. Internal Communication

AfriConEU partners have been using the tools and following up on the strategies indicated in D1.1 with the goal of ensuring that the flow of information and sharing among partners is **consistent, regular and efficient**.

Although several channels are available to ease the communication among partners, specifically considering the wide geographical dispersion, the most used tools both for internal communication and document sharing are still the **SharePoint** working space, **Online meetings** and **E-mail communication**.

4.1. SharePoint

The online working space set up within MStTeams continues to be used daily for communication and documents management and exchange within the AfriConEU partners. This SharePoint is accessible only to those invited by the Project Coordinator and granted access and permissions are provided by the Coordinator team members.

The SharePoint is composed of several folders with specific purposes (Figure 2):

- **Admin Docs folder** – in this folder, partners can consult the GA (original and after the amendment request) and the CA;
- **Meetings folder** – all the agendas, presentations and attendance reports from all the meetings held so far are available in this folder;
- **WP folders** – all WPs have a single folder where all documents concerning the specific activities and tasks of the WP. The correspondent deliverables of each WP are also included in these folders.
- **Documents in the root folder** – there are 3 different excel files in the root folder of the AfriConEU SharePoint related to project management:
 - **(1) Contacts** – where all partners list the members of their team that are engaged in the AfriConEU project. Each partner has the responsibility to update the contact information of their respective team. An up-to-date contact file ensures that everyone involved in the project receives the AfriConEU communications and that no one is left off the communications loop;
 - **(2) Gantt** – where partners can consult an updated overview of the timeline of the project's activities, deliverables and milestones;
 - **(3) Milestones and risks** – where partners can keep track of the status of the milestones of the project and regularly monitor the identified risks (or add new ones).

Nome	Modificado	Modificado por
Admin Docs	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
Meetings	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP2 - Context and SoA	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP3 - AfriConEU Academy	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP4 - Roll Out	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP5 - Results Uptake	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP6 - Com_Dissemination	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
Contacts_AfriConEU_Global.xlsx	6 days ago	youthmakershub
GANTT_Updated_08022021.xlsx	8 de fevereiro	Ana Solange Leal
Milestones & Risks.xlsx	15 de fevereiro	Ana Solange Leal

Figure 2 - AfriConEU SharePoint at MSTeams

Concerning the naming and numbering of the project documents, the consortium has been following the rules in a consistent manner, following the guidelines indicated in D1.1 (and that are described below):

- To identify a document version, the date should be used, with the format DDMMYYYY;
- Name segments should be separated by _ and the acronym of the project that identifies the project should be included. For example, the draft version of Deliverable D1.2 produced on 15 July 2022 would be: **AfriConEU_D1.2_15072022_V01.doc.**;
- When sharing a revised version of the document, the partner that has provided suggestions and inputs, should include its acronym before sending the new version to the remaining partners: **AfriConEU_D1.2_15072022_V01_ECA.doc.**;
- When the document is in its final version, then the naming should be **AfriConEU_D1.2_DDMMYYYY_FV.doc.**

Partners also use **SharePoint as a Forum** and make some posts to interact with the rest of the consortium (either to share some achievements or relevant events related to the project's aim, ask for feedback in more practical questions, etc.). This system has been proved to be quite effective for more informal communications.

4.2. Meetings

The consortium partners have **Monthly Monitoring Meetings** that are held on every first Tuesday of the month (in an online format, through MS Teams), to observe and verify the work progress made in each of the WPs/Tasks. By the time this report is being submitted,

partners have been meeting every month (with some adjustments regarding the dates, whenever necessary). These meetings allow for an updated project status on a regular basis, as well as the opportunity to discuss operational and administrative issues in a timely fashion. After each meeting, written minutes are produced and circulated among partners with conclusions of discussions held and information about the next steps in the project.

As for the **consortium meetings** that were planned to take place in physical format, due to the covid-19 pandemic situation on both continents (Europe and Africa) during 2021 and 2022, unfortunately they could not be held to date. But the monthly monitoring meetings (that now have 2 hours duration instead of the 1 hour and a half initially scheduled) allow for the consortium to have a close and regular contact to compensate for the lack of physical interaction. Nonetheless, a two-day online consortium meeting was organised in March 2022 in order to do an in-depth overview of the 1st year of the project and take strategic decisions for the 3rd phase of the project – the roll-out implementation of the AfriConEU Academy Flagship Programmes. Also, a physical consortium meeting is being organised to take place in the fall of 2022.

During the first year and a half of the project, several bilateral meetings between partners were held whenever necessary to ensure the smooth running of project activities.

4.3. E-mail communication

The main communication channel between AfriConEU partners is through email. The consortium continues to follow the best practices indicated in D1.1:

- To facilitate the recognition of electronic messages related to the project, partners should standardise the subject title as follows: acronym of the project + subject [**AfriConEU | Meeting Notes**];
- Partners are encouraged to use the MSTeams SharePoint to store files and preferably send emails only with the respective link;
- E-mails should be sent with the knowledge of the coordinator/management partners (which is why an updated contact file is crucial, as mentioned in section 4.1).

4.4. Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution procedures are included in the CA, in line with responsibilities defined within the organisational structure of the project. By the time this report is being produced, all disagreements were solved at the lowest level and amicably by reaching a consensus with all partners.

Nonetheless, if in the future an agreement cannot be reached at a task or WP level, the Project Coordinator will mediate. If that does not work, then the Steering Committee will make a decision.

Negotiation and decisions taken by consensus are and will always be the main tools to resolve conflicts. Should this approach and a majority decision not be achievable by the parties involved and the rest of the Consortium, an independent referee shall be appointed by the Project Coordinator. These conflict resolution procedures will be carried out in accordance with Article 11.8 of the CA.

5. Reporting

In order for the Commission/Agency to verify that the project is implemented properly, the beneficiaries must submit any information requested, and in particular, the deliverables and reports detailed in the GA. In this sense, two levels of reporting were implemented in the course of the action: **Internal** and **External** Reporting.

5.1 Internal Reporting

Every nine months, partners shall report to the PC the progress made in that specific period, namely regarding main achievements, financial execution, deviations from plans and anticipated actions for the following period.

Since the project started, partners have already submitted the 1st internal reporting period to the PC (which covered M1-M9) and are at the time preparing the 2nd Internal Report that will cover M10-M18. Both of them will be considered major inputs for the 1st external reporting to the EC.

The timing for the next internal reporting periods is as follows:

- M19 – M25 – 3rd Internal Report
- M26 – M36 – 4th Internal Report

5.2 External Reporting

AfriConEU project has two Official Reporting Periods when a periodic report (technical + financial) must be submitted to the EC via the Funding & Tenders Portal:

- M1 – M18 – Interim Report (Feb.21-Jul.22)
- M19 – M36 – Final Report (Aug.22-Jan24)

The technical report shall include an explanation of the work carried out, an overview of the progress and a summary for publication. Report on work progress is to be collected by WPL and provided to the PC, who will be responsible for integrating all inputs and producing the final report. Before submission to the EC, the report is to be validated by all partners.

The PC is at the moment preparing the first Interim Report which will be presented in the Project Interim Review Meeting that will take place online on 4 October 2022.

6. Quality Procedures

6.1 Performance Indicators

As described in D1.1, for each of the Specific Objectives (SO) of the project, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been elaborated. They have been monitored closely by the PC and WPLs in order to ensure the implementation of tasks in the most suitable manner to achieve these targets and the overall objectives, thus maximising the impact of the action.

In **Table 3** there is an overview of the status of each one of the KPIs indicated:

- Achieved (DX.X): in the cases that the KPI was already met and is documented in one of the deliverables of the project;
- To be Achieved: in the cases that the consortium is still working to meet the KPI.

Table 3 - AfriConEU Key Performance Indicators Status

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification	Status
SO1: Explore the digital innovation ecosystem in Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana, and Tanzania and analyse local DIHs needs so as to create tailor-made programmes for transforming local hubs into catalysts for digital transformation and entrepreneurship	In depth interviews with DIHs managers, entrepreneurs, policy makers from Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania to analyse the local innovation ecosystems.	>60 interviews	Achieved (D2.1)
	Online survey of targeted innovation ecosystem stakeholders to records needs and challenges of DIHs	>200 responses	Achieved (D2.1)
	Roundtable discussions in Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania with representatives from startups, SMEs, DIHs, government, investor networks etc.	4 roundtables – 40 participants	Achieved (D2.1)
	In depth interviews with trainers of existing capacity building programmes targeted to DIHs from Africa and Europe	>20 interviews	Achieved (D2.3)
	Interviews with trainees (i.e. DIHs managers and staff) of existing capacity building programmes targeted to DIHs from Africa and Europe	>100 interviews	Achieved (D2.3)
	Report analysing the local innovation ecosystems in Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana and Tanzania	1 per country	Achieved (D2.1)
	Number of DIHs Capacity Building programmes identified and listed in the project's online data base	>50	Achieved (D2.2)

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification	Status
SO2: Develop the Flagship Programme on Capacity Building for African DIHs and support thus their further development as well as their potential to drive the digitalization process	Capacity building sub-programmes covering DIHs business models, multi-actor approach, technology transfer, startups finance and digital skills	4 subprogrammes	Achieved (D3.1)
	Capacity building webinars	20 webinars	Achieved (D3.3)
	Online repository of capacity building resources and ready to use training material	1 repository	Achieved (D3.4)
	Local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	12 workshops	Achieved (D3.2)
	Online Masterclasses for supporting African DIHs potential/ Number of external speakers for each one of the topics (AI, IOT, etc).	8 master classes/min. 8 speakers	Achieved (D3.5)
SO3: Develop the Flagship Programme on Trans-continental Partnerships Development and enforce cooperation on an equal footing between African and European DIHs	Online focus groups & number of participants discussing about challenges and opportunities for EU - Africa partnership building (T2.3)	3 focus groups & 30 participants	Achieved (D2.4)
	International participative design workshop among DIHs, experts, investors, entrepreneurs etc. to discuss on the design of the Trans-continental Partnership Development programmes	1 workshop & 20 participants	Achieved (D3.6)
	Trans-continental partnership development sub-programmes covering thematic issues such as investment and market opportunities in Africa, youth and employment opportunities etc.	3 subprogrammes ¹	Achieved (D3.6)
	Design thinking thematic bootcamps between DIHs and innovation stakeholders from Africa and Europe	1 per African country (4 total)	Achieved (D3.6)
	International Brokerage event between DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors and the African Diaspora communities in Europe	1	Achieved (D3.6)
	Capitalisation and celebration event	1	Achieved (D3.6)
SO4: Organise and deliver capacity building, knowledge sharing and new partnership development	Number of stakeholders reached through the engagement activities	>1000 (a min. of 60% from Africa)	To be Achieved
	Number of participants in the 20 Capacity Building Webinars	>300 (a min. of 70% from Africa)	To be Achieved
	Number of participants in 8 Online Masterclasses	>200 (a min. of 70% from Africa)	To be Achieved

¹ In the course of the AfriConEU trans-continental partnership development sub-programmes and taking into consideration the needs and challenges reported in WP2, it was decided to deliver 4 different subprogrammes.

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification	Status
activities among African and European DIHs and contribute towards a vibrant digital economy and new job opportunities for the benefit of both continents	Number of participants in the 12 local networking and training workshops	>200	To be Achieved
	Number of participants in the 4 design-thinking bootcamps	>160 in total	To be Achieved
	Number of joint projects developed during the bootcamps	>30	To be Achieved
	Number of attendees in the International Brokerage Event	>200	To be Achieved
	Number of connections for strategic partnerships made during the Brokerage event	>10	To be Achieved
	Number of attendees in the Final Capitalisation and Celebration Event	>400	To be Achieved
	Number of stakeholders and final beneficiaries involved in evaluation activities	>1000	To be Achieved
SO5: Engage African and European DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors, and policy makers in a community of networked ecosystems that will foster the sustainability of the project results and the exploitation of opportunities between the two continents.	Number of stakeholders reached through the Online AfriconEU Community	>3000	To be Achieved
	Connections made for exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU the online community	>200	To be Achieved
	Number of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives	>40	To be Achieved
SO6: Foster the diffusion and uptake of the AfriConEU Academy within and beyond the targeted countries, contributing thus to the realization of the “AU-EU digital economy partnership”	AfriConEU Deployment Toolkit offering standardized resources for enabling any DIHs re-use them	1	To be Achieved
	Policy roundtables and number of participants	4 / >20	To be Achieved
	Policy recommendations Report and number of policy makers reached	1/ >100	To be Achieved
	Exploitation and sustainability strategy	>1	To be Achieved
	Dissemination and Communication Plan	1	To be Achieved
	Number of unique visits to the AfriConEU website	>1000/month	To be Achieved
	YouTube channel videos /views	10 / 5000	To be Achieved
	Promotional Material distributed during project/external events	>1000	To be Achieved

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification	Status
	Number of followers in social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter).	>2700	To be Achieved
	Number of Newsletters	>8	To be Achieved
	Number of Press releases	>20	To be Achieved

6.2 Milestones

A set of milestones were also defined to monitor the project progress. Table below present the list of milestones to be achieved in the next project period, the partners responsible and the means of verification.

Table 4 - AfriConEU Project Milestones for the period M18-M36

No	Milestone name	WP	Partner	Estimated date	Means of verification
MS5	Successful review and reporting acceptance	1	INOVA+	M20	Successful Interim review by the EC
MS9	Implementation of International brokerage Event	4	STIMMU LI	M20	D4.5 Brokerage event report
MS10	1,000,000 Social Media impressions	6	YMH	M24	D6.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan – Third version
MS11	Successful interim review and reporting acceptance	1	INOVA+	M24	Successful Interim review by the EC
MS12	Last Webinar delivered	4	STIMMU LI	M26	D4.4 Webinars report
MS13	Completion of implementation of local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	4	STIMMU LI	M26	D4.3 Networking and knowledge sharing events report
MS14	Implementation of 4 Design Thinking Bootcamps	4	STIMMU LI	M26	Programme of the bootcamps published on the website
MS15	1st Online Masterclass delivered	4	STIMMU LI	M28	Programme of the online masterclass published on the website
MS16	Completion of implementation of 4 Design Thinking Bootcamps	4	STIMMU LI	M29	D4.6 Design thinking bootcamps report
MS17	Last Online Masterclass delivered	4	STIMMU LI	M30	D4.7 Online Masterclass report
MS18	AfriConEU Community with 1000 members	5	BUNI	M35	D5.2 The AfriConEU community report
MS19	Successful preparation of final report	1	INOVA+	M36	Final report submitted on time

6.3 Deliverables Revision

Deliverables are products of the project and also the evidence of the project’s performance that enables the Commission to monitor the project’s progress, implementation and impact. Deliverables are identified in Annex 1 to the GA per WP and must be submitted according to the timetable specified in the table hereafter.

The AfriConEU partners are following the procedure indicated in **D1.1** to build on a participatory and iterative approach to ensure the active involvement of all project partners in the development and production of the project’s deliverables:

- Whenever relevant, draft deliverables are sent to all consortium members for feedback allowing them at least one week to reply;
- Each WP leader should ensure that the deliverable final draft is ready and circulated to the Steering Committee by the responsible partner **at least 2 weeks before the due date** (see deliverable list – Table 4).
- Reviewer member should send their final comments to the partner responsible for the deliverable **within one week**.
- The partner responsible for the deliverable must then send the very final version of the deliverable **at least 3 working days before the due date** to the PC and PMO.
- The final decision on the deliverables is taken by the PC, and PMO is the person responsible for uploading the deliverable on the Funding & Tenders Portal at the **latest on the due date and informing the EC**.

Table 5 - AfriConEU List of Deliverables for the period M18-M36

No	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date	Responsible partner	Reviewer partner
1.2	Management and Quality Plan - Year 2	1	M18	INOVA+	All partners
1.3	Management and Quality Plan - Year 3	1	M30	INOVA+	All partners
1.5	Data Management Plan - Year 2	1	M18	INOVA+	ITC
1.6	Data Management Plan - Year 3	1	M36	INOVA+	ITC
1.7	Innovation and IPR Management Strategy (Interim)	1	M20	INOVA+	PBS
1.8	Innovation and IPR Management Strategy (Final)	1	M36	INOVA+	PBS
4.3	Networking and knowledge sharing events report	4	M26	Hapa	DPixel
4.4	Webinars report	4	M26	PBS	YMH
4.5	Brokerage Event report	4	M20	DPixel	INOVA+
4.6	Design thinking bootcamps report	4	M29	INOVA+	Stimmuli
4.7	Online Masterclass report	4	M30	ITC	PBS
4.8	Capitalisation and Celebration event report	4	M33	DPixel	YMH

No	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date	Responsible partner	Reviewer partner
4.9	Monitoring and assessment methodology	4	M19	Stimmuli	INOVA+
4.10	Impact assessment results	4	M34	Stimmuli	PBS
5.2	The AfriConEU Community Report (Final)	5	M35	INOVA+	BUNI
5.3	The AfriConEU Deployment Toolkit	5	M36	Stimmuli	PBS
5.4	AfriConEU Policy Recommendations	5	M27	BUNI	INOVA+
5.5	Blueprint on DIHs transcontinental cooperation	5	M36	ATBN	ITC
6.3	Dissemination and communication Plan - Third version	6	M28	YMH	INOVA+
6.4	Dissemination and communication Plan - Final version	6	M36	YMH	Stimmuli
6.8	Electronic newsletter – Third Release	6	M18	YMH	Outbox
6.9	Electronic newsletter – Fourth Release	6	M24	YMH	BUNI
6.10	Electronic newsletter – Fifth Release	6	M30	YMH	HAPA
6.11	Electronic newsletter – Sixth Release	6	M36	YMH	ATBN
6.12	Synergies creation plan and report (Interim)	6	M25	ATBN	YMH
6.13	Synergies creation plan and report (Final)	6	M34	ATBN	Outbox
6.14	Exploitation and sustainability plan (Interim)	6	M25	INOVA+	PBS
6.15	Exploitation and sustainability plan (Final)	6	M36	INOVA+	ITC

6.4 Project Templates

Partners are using the provided templates for project documents and presentations in order to facilitate their production, guarantee the consistency and quality of AfriConEU image and ensure that all documents produced in the framework of the project carry the mention of EU funding in the requested format.

Small changes and updates are being performed whenever deemed necessary to standardise the project image and branding.

7. Risk Management

At the beginning of the project, the AfriConEU consortium identified a list of potential risks and related mitigation measures that is available on the project SharePoint to be updated on *ad hoc* basis, whenever new risks are identified.

To perform the analysis and monitoring of the identified risks, the consortium uses the Risk Register Template (Annex 1) which is being verified regularly every 4 months in the monthly monitoring meetings.

In [Annex 2](#) it can be assessed the latest version of the Risk Management file, taking into consideration the last time it was updated (prior to the start of the Academy events in May). As it can be found, the risk status is not high for any of the potential risks identified and mitigation measures are foreseen (and in some cases were implemented in the cases of WP2 and WP3, which have already ended).

8. Conclusion

In this report, updates, deviations and a brief status on the Management and Quality Plan (D1.1) ongoing plan were presented.

From the document, it is possible to conclude that the best practices and procedures that were adopted at the beginning of the project continue to be implemented with success, while also adapting to the unforeseen circumstances that occurred in the last 18 months.

The consortium will continue to improve its processes whenever necessary and implement new practices that may enhance the management and quality of the AfriConEU project (which will be reflected in the upcoming version of this report, D1.3).

Annex 1: Risk Register Template

Description of Risk	Probability			Impact			Risk Status	Mitigation Measure/Plan	Responsibility	Action Req'd	
	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low				Yes	No

Annex 2: Last update of the Risk Register file

Number	Description	Probability			IMPACT			Risk Status	Risk Mitigation Measures	Responsibility	Action Req'd	
		High (2-3)	Medium (1)	Low (0.5)	High (2-3)	Medium (1)	Low (0.5)				Yes	No
WP1 - Project Management												
1	Financial risks related to the implementation of the project			0,5		1		1,5	Financial management will not be limited to reporting but it will include a close monitoring so as to be able to identify early signs of concern	INOVA + All partners		
2	Changes in the project team			0,5	2			2,5	The PC will require from partners to include substitutes with equivalent (or higher) qualifications and experience and inform them in detail about the project, their role and responsibilities	INOVA + All partners		
WP2 - Context and state of the art analysis												
3	Difficulties in data collection and research activities			0,5	2			2,5	The consortium includes partners already involved in the local innovation ecosystems to be explored and they will advise the design of the research activities. If difficulties arise, local partners will pay more efforts to reach out to the stakeholders needed for collecting research data.	ATBN + ITC + Outbox		
WP3 - Development of the AfriConEU Academy												
4	Difficulties in designing tailor made training offerings		1		2			3	African partners will be actively involved in designing the training offering of the Academy. If needed, they shall engage more stakeholders from their local context to participate in the design process.	PBS + BUNI + Hapa + Outbox		
WP4 - Roll out implementation and assessment												
5	Ongoing force majeure (e.g. Health crisis) preventing physical capacity building, and partnership events	2				1		3	The consortium has already designed an online alternative for effective engagement and involvement of stakeholders in the AfriConEU Academy activities. In addition, the consortium has already foreseen dedicated activities for COVID-19	Partners responsible for organising events		
6	Lack of coordination during implementation due to the large number of stakeholders and activities involved.			0,5		1		1,5	WP4 leader will be responsible to monitor all the implementation activities and ensure the transfer of all necessary information to local hub coordinators. In case of misunderstanding, personal meetings will be implemented.	INOVA + All partners		
7	Quality of events and number of DIHs, startups and other stakeholders attending activities are below expectations			0,5		1		1,5	WP4 leader will continuously evaluate the processes. The PC will analyse results and take action in order to continuously improve the procedures. AfriConEU launches a new round of the activity, after evaluation, contact DIHs, startups, networks etc. directly in order to understand what is attractive & unattractive about the activities	INOVA + All partners		
8	Low number of new partnerships among DIHs, startups, investors etc.			0,5		1		1,5	Identify the causes and explore new networks/contact to reach the target. Organize new matchmaking events.	All partners		
WP5 - Community development and results uptake												
9	Not enough evaluation data are gathered.			0,5	2			2,5	Monitoring and evaluation will start from the beginning of the implementation stage and will be conducted by Stimuli's expert team in large scale evaluation and impact assessment studies.	BUNI + All partners		
WP6 - Communication and Dissemination												
10	Ongoing dissemination may take more effort and resources than planned			0,5	2			2,5	The PC with the DM will continually monitor partners use of dissemination resources	YMH + INOVA		A new communication strategy was developed in order to increase social media impressions. The target audience of all social media will be more engaged and create content for AfriConEU so as to increase the impressions and reach the milestone of 500,000 social media impressions.